

AN OVERVIEW OF VERTEBRATE DIVERSITY OF KARACHI EAST WITH REFERENCE TO ENVIRONMENTAL HAZARDS AND ANTHROPOGENICAL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract

In the present study, the effects of anthropogenic activities and environmental hazards on the biodiversity of Karachi East were carried out during the period of one year (January 2024 to December 2024). Because of the Indus basin, the Karachi coast offers a wide range of vertebrate diversity, including habitat for threatened, endangered, and critically endangered species, a resting, feeding, breeding, and wintering area for migratory bird species, a high species richness area, a biodiversity spawning and nursery area, and a traditional and culturally significant area. However, there has been a significant loss of biodiversity in recent years due to rapid industrialization. 10 species of mammals belong to 08 families and 04 orders. There are a total of 37 species of birds and 32 genera belonging to 23 families comprising 09 orders, and 08 species of reptiles belonging to 6 families comprising 01 order. During the study period, 03 species of amphibians and 03 genera belonging to 02 families, 01 order, 61 species of plants and 51 genera were recorded from Karachi East. Habitat destruction and alteration, deforestation, improper waste disposal, rapid urbanization, and a lack of awareness about the importance of wildlife among local people were all serious threats to biodiversity.

INTRODUCTION

Biodiversity referred to the diversity of life on earth. They interact with one another and with their environment. Biodiversity enhances the ecosystem efficiency; all species in that ecosystem, regardless of size, play an important role. Biodiversity is essential for human survival and economic well-being, as well as for the structure, functioning, and stability of ecosystems. It is a valuable resource because it provides both goods and services to society, such as food, water, wood

products, ornamental plants, breeding stocks, population reservoirs, air and water purification, soil fertility, pest control, biological productivity, climate regulation, waste degradation, nutrient cycling, recreation and ecotourism, and medicine. A diverse ecosystem has the ability to both prevent and recover from a wide range of disasters.

Biodiversity can be evaluated and tracked at various spatial scales: alpha diversity (measured

the numbers and diversity of individuals within a habitat unit), beta diversity (expression of diversity between habitats), gamma diversity (diversity of habitats within a landscape or region). Genetic diversity (Gene variation within species and populations), species diversity (total number of species in a given area, measures in term of species richness), and ecosystem diversity (diversity among ecosystems such as wetlands, grasslands, hot deserts, cold deserts, temperate forests, tropical forests, and others) are the three levels of biodiversity that are typically investigated (Magurran, 2004). The complexity of life on Earth is created by these three levels working together.

Currently, 35 biodiversity hotspots have been discovered around the world, the majority of which are found in tropical forests (Gorenflo, 2012). A biodiversity hotspot is an area with an unusually high concentration of species, many of which are endemic (Myers 1988). Humans pose a significant threat to its biodiversity. Biodiversity is negatively impacted by serious environmental hazards caused by anthropogenic activities such as deforestation, habitat destruction and degradation, overgrazing, illegal hunting and population depletion of wild species, introduction of invasive species, cutting of vegetation, human population growth, pollution and disease, over-exploitation of natural resources, global climate change, energy crises, international trade of game species, and a lack of strong incentives. Many species are now endangered or critically endangered as a result of these negative impacts, and others have been reduced to small and dispersed populations..

Status of Biodiversity in Pakistan

Pakistan is located in northwestern part of the subcontinent South Asia and is at the junction of Central Asia and Middle East, which gives its location great significance. Pakistan comprises both Palearctic and Oriental region (Roberts, 1991). It is a country with a wide range of geophysical and meteorological characteristics. From the Himalayas to the sea level coastal mangrove forests, a system of natural wetlands

and adjacent habitat supports a diverse range of animals and vegetation. These mangrove forests act as a natural barrier for coastal areas that are densely populated, as well as a nursery ground for aquatic species. (Khurshid, 2004).

Due to its varied land structure, Pakistan provides a wide range of habitat for various bird species. This diversity of habitats supports a wide range of bird species, 669 of which have been documented. Pakistan comprises both Palearctic and the Oriental (Roberts, 1991). Different researchers have provided varying estimates of Pakistan's vertebrate diversity. Roberts (1997) identified 176 Mammal species in Pakistan. While there are 195 species of mammals from 10 orders have been recorded in Pakistan (Roberts, 2005; Altaf *et al.*, 2014). According to Rehman and Iffat (1997), Pakistan has 179 species of reptilian fauna, including tortoises, crocodiles, gavials, lizards, and snakes. In Pakistan, Khan (2004) discovered 22 species of Amphibians in Pakistan, belonging three families: *Bufo*idae, *Rana*idae, and *Microhylidae*.

The total number of bird's species in Pakistan is 606 belonging to 272 genera and 74 families (Ali and Ripley 1987). According to Robert (1991) there are about 660 bird's species present in Pakistan. Grimmett *et al.* (2008) count 670 birds' species in Pakistan. Avian diversity is one of the most significant environmental indicators to assess the quality of any habitat (Bird Life International, 2013). Aside from that, a large number of migratory birds visit Pakistan every winter and settle on the coasts of interior water bodies in Sindh and Baluchistan. They are very important from a variety of perspectives, but they also carry a variety of viral, bacterial, fungal, and protozoan zoonotic agents and play an important role in the epidemiology of human-associated zoonosis.

Pakistan is home to more than 195 reptile species including crocodiles, lizards, chameleons, geckos, turtles, skinks, and tortoises. Out of these species, 13 species are endemic to Pakistan. Due to habitat loss, hunting, poaching and illegal trade,

some of these species are threatened while others are facing the risk of extinction.

Status of Biodiversity in Sindh

Sindh is the largest province of Pakistan by area, stretching about 579 kilometers from north to south and 442 kilometers from east to west, with an area of 140,915 square kilometer of Pakistan territory. There are 29 districts in the province and Total tehsils in Sindh are 138 (Census 2017). The province of Sindh forms the lower Indus basin and lies between 23° 35' and 28° 30' northern latitude and 66° 42' and 71° 10' east longitude (Khan *et al.*, 2014). The different ecosystems of Sindh include wetlands, deserts, river, mangrove forests, agricultural and coastal areas. The River Indus act as a key source of water in Pakistan and majority of the population of Sindh depends on this River. There are many canals and barrages coming out of this River and giving lives to wetland birds all over the Sindh (Yahya, 2007).

Sindh estuarine and coastal wetlands serve as nursery grounds for the lobsters, shrimps and fish. Each year during the migration season, over one million of water birds belonging to 108 species, visit Sindh wetlands (Khan, 2006). The monsoon influences the coastal climate, which is tropical and dry. The average rainfall on Sindh's coast is 220 mm. (<https://www.worlddata.info/asia/pakistan/climate-sindh.php>, 2018).

Sindh's landscape consists mostly of alluvial plains flanking the Indus River, the Thar Desert in the eastern portion of the province closest to the border with India, and the Kirthar Mountains in the western part of Sindh. Sindh's climate is recorded for hot summers and mild winters. Sindh has Pakistan's largest city and financial hub, the Karachi.

Ghalib *et al.* (2018) recorded 82 species of mammals, 420 species of birds, 103 species of reptiles, 7 species of amphibians and 33 important plant species from Sindh. The key species include: Sind Wild Goat, Urial,

Chinkara, Leopard, Bluebull, Hog Deer, Hyaena, Caracal, Honey Badger, Fishing Cat, Desert Fox, Indus Dolphin, Humpback Dolphin, Indian Peafowl, Sarus Crane, Houbara Bustard, Marbled Teal, Grey Partridge, Chakur, Indian Whitebacked Vulture, Indian Longbilled Vulture, Shaheen Falcon, Marsh Crocodile, Green Turtle, Olive Ridley Turtle, Indian Python, Desert Monitor, Fat tailed Gecko, Spiny tailed Lizard and Freshwater Turtles. The major threats to the wildlife of the Province are: poaching, habitat degradation and lack of management. A total of 40 threatened wildlife species have been recorded.

Javed and Rehman (2004) observed the status of marsh crocodile in Sindh. Khan *et al.* (2015) studied the mammalian fauna in the desert lands of Tharparkar, Sindh and recorded thirty five (35) species from different habitats of the district, majority of which belonged to order Rodentia followed by Carnivora. Khan and Mahmood (2003), Khan and Mahmood (2004), Rehman *et al.* (2004), Khan *et al.* (2005), Khan *et al.* (2010), Khan and Hussain (2011), Khan *et al.* (2012), Sheikh *et al.* (2013), Minton (1962) have been done a lot of work on herpatofauna of Karachi, Coast Sindh.

Rais *et al.* (2010) studied some free-living medium-sized and large mammals in the Chotiari Reservoir and its surroundings in the district of Sanghar, Sindh, belonging from two orders, Carnivora and Artiodactyla, and found the evidence for thirteen species out of which Indian wolf and the striped hyena are thought to be extinct while smooth-coated otter, Indian desert cat, caracal, and fishing cat were the rare species of the reservoir.

A lot of work on the avifauna of Sindh has been done by Roberts *et al.* (1986), Khanum and Ahmed (1988), Roberts (1991-92), Ghalib and Hasnain (1994, 1997,1997a), Hasnain and Ghalib (1997), Ahmed *et al.* (1999), Ghalib *et al.* (2000), Siddiqui *et al.* (2001), Khan (2005), Mirza (2007), Durrane *et al.* (2008), Grimmett *et al.* (2008), Ghalib and Nawaz (2008), Ghalib *et al.* (2009), Abbas *et al.* (2010), Hassan and Javed

(2011), Khan et al. (2012). The Ministry of Climate Changes Pakistan Wetland Program (2012), Ahmed (2013) and Begum *et al.* (2013). Afghan *et al.* (2015) reported incidences of bird's population Tandojam, Sindh, Pakistan.

Status of biodiversity in Karachi

Karachi is the capital of Sindh province. Karachi is located on the coast line of Sindh province in the southern Pakistan, along a natural harbor on the Arabian Sea. . The city has six districts including East, West, South, and Central, Malir and Korangi District. Karachi is built on a Coastal Plains with scattered rocky outcroppings, hills and coastal marshlands. The Karachi coast is significant because it provide habitat for threatened, endangered and critically endangered species, a resting, feeding, breeding, wintering area, passage for migratory bird species, a high species richness area, a biodiversity spawning and nursery area, and a traditional and cultural significance area. (Khan, 2018). Karachi city has two small ranges, the Khasa hills and the Mulri hills. Karachi has an arid climate dominated by long summer season while moderated by oceanic influence from the Arabian Sea.

Khan et al. (2018) studied the distribution and status of the vertebrate biodiversity of Korangi and Phitti creeks, Karachi coast, Sindh, Pakistan. Hussain (2009) recorded 27 reptilian species in Karachi Coast including 3 turtles, 9 lizards and 15 snakes. Durraneet et al (2008) observed the birds of Sandspit/Hawkesbay coastal wetland Complex, Karachi Coast and recorded 114 species of birds, belonging to 14 Orders and 38 Families. Feroz and Hadi (2016) studied the Species diversity and abundance of resident and migratory bird fauna of a North-Western Peri-Urban Area of Karachi and recorded 26 avian species with a total count of individuals of N=6515. Khan *et al.* (2014) recorded 172 species of birds in Karachi including 71 water birds, 46 passerines, 28 birds of prey, 9 game birds and 18 other birds.

Hashmi et al. (2013) studied the status, distribution and threats of *Varanus* Species

(*Varanus bengalensis* and *Varanus griseus*) in Karachi and Thatta of Sindh and find out that both the species were being threatened by human activities and main threats were degradation of natural habitats, disturbans from villagers and hunters.

Abbas et al. (2010) find out the first record of of spotted munia (*Lonchura punctulata*) in Karachi as well as in Sindh province. Shaukat and Raza (2016) recorded a total of 49 bird species in Karachi University campus, belonging to 12 orders and 27 families. The objective of the present study was to investigate the status of vertebrate diversity of Karachi east with reference to environmental hazards and anthropogenical activities.

Methodology

Ground surveys were carried out during the current study, which is most reliable for counting of biodiversity (Howes and Blackwell, 1989). The study area was divided into sub units included the urban, peri-urban areas, residential areas, industrial areas and barren lands.

Primary Data

Primary data was collected by gathering information by visiting and employing various observation techniques. Such as birds were counted by Point count, Line transect and Look and see methods as earlier as these methodologies were used by Sarar et al. (2009) in Dhaka, Bangladesh, Line transect and point count methods were used by Bibby et al. (1992) in India and (Ghalib *et al.*, 2008) in Hingol National Park, Balochistan, Pakistan.

1. Direct Sighting

Direct observations can be done through many techniques but the following techniques have been followed.

Inventory

A detailed list has been prepared about complete ecology of study areas. All Abiotic and biotic factors has been recorded including Temperature,

Humidity, and Wind direction. Biotic factors included fauna and flora. Vegetation present in study area were identified and noted.

Point Count

Point count is one of several methods used to inventory and monitor bird populations. A point count is a tally of all birds detected by sight and sound by a single observer located at a fixed position during a specified period.

Habitat Searching/Line transect

A transect is a path along which one count and record occurrences of the species of study (e.g. reptiles). It requires an observer to move along a fixed path and at the same time (in some procedure), obtain the distance of the object from the path.

Noosing

Noosing is used to observe many reptiles because many lizards and snakes are most visible when they are active. Some lizards such as Varanids may sleep or bask in places that are difficult to reach, such as in the canopy and large stones or in burrows. In this situation, a noose may be used to observe them.

Sampling estimation

This method included the counting of birds as and when encountered. This method depends on encounter rate (sighting per km) and call index. In this method roost count was also adopted in which total numbers of birds arriving at the roost were counted. This method is assumed much more accurate than encounter rate method. Binocular with power of 999980 XS were used for spotting the birds some distance away or high up in the sky.

2. Indirect Sighting

It includes the presence of signs and tracks, trails and fecal materials, traces, nests burrows and carcass of dead specimen.

Secondary Data

It includes secondary information from other sources like interviews from local communities, review of the published literature. Interview's has been conducted to get the detailed information about the species, habits and abundance of Vertebrate fauna. Collection of secondary data involved the information taken from local peoples.

Results

In the Present investigation, population and diversity of fauna (reptiles, avifauna and mammalian fauna) were studied. Over all 10 species of mammals belonging to 8 families and 4 orders, total 37 species of birds and 32 genera belonging to 23 families comprising 9 orders, 8 species of reptiles belonging to 6 families comprising 1 order While 3 species of amphibians and 3 genera belonging to 2 families, 1 order and 61 species of plants and 51 genera were recorded from the Karachi East during the study period. The maximum mean annual temperature recorded 30.4 Degree Celsius. The mean minimum temperature recorded 21.2. The maximum mean annual precipitation recorded 149.8. The mean minimum precipitation recorded 18.2. The mean relative Humidity recorded 69.2.

Total species of birds recorded previously (Year 2013) =38

Total species of birds recorded previously (Year 2016) =49

Status of the birds recorded Total species of birds recorded (Year 2018) =37

No previous data available about mammalian, reptilian and amphibian fauna of the campus.

To describe bird's species diversity in the campus we use Shannon's function (Shannon and Weaver 1963). This expression is

$$H' = - \log p_i$$

$$s \text{ (number of species)} = 37$$

$$N \text{ (total number of individuals)} = 1067.3$$

Σ (sum) of pi =1073.295315
 Σ (n/N) = 1073.295

Σ (sum) of pi ln pi = 1149827.46
H = -1149827.

Table 1. The Mean Maximum and Minimum Temperature of Karachi in Year 2024

YEAR	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	OCT	NOV	DEC	MEAN
MEAN MONTHLY MAXIMUM TEMPERATURE (MEAN DAILY MAXIMUM TEMPERATURE (CALSIUS))													
2024	25.0	26.1	29.4	32.2	33.9	33.9	32.8	31.1	31.1	32.8	30.6	26.7	30.4
MEAN MONTHLY MINIMUM TEMPERATURE (MEAN DAILY MINIMUM TEMPERATURE (CALSIUS))													
2024	12.8	14.4	19.4	22.8	26.1	27.8	27.2	26.1	25.0	22.2	17.8	13.9	21.2

Table 2. The Mean Maximum and Minimum Precipitation of Karachi in Year 2024.

YEAR	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	OCT	NOV	DE C	ANNUAL
MEAN MONTHLY MAXIMUM PRECIPITATION (mm)													
2024	69	51	56	131	60	183	392	428	252	69	41	66	149.8
MEAN MONTHLY MINIMUM PRECIPITATION (mm)													
2024	13	16	12	18	21	18	14	17	23	18	26	23	18.2

Table 3. The Mean Relative Humidity of Karachi in Year 2024.

YEAR	JAN	FEB	MARC	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	OCT	NOV	DE C	ANNUAL
MEAN RELATIVE HUMIDITY (%)													
2024	54	61	58	75	78	78	81	82	80	70	59	55	69.2

Table 4. Status of mammalian species observed

Orders	Family	Scientific Name	Common Name	Status
Lagomorpha	Leporidae	<i>Lepus nigricollis</i>	Indian Hare	Less Common
Insectivora	Erinaceidae	<i>Hemiechinus collaris</i>	Indian long eared Hedgehog	Less Common
Rodentia	Hystricidae	<i>Hystrix indica</i>	Indian Crested Porcupine	Near Threatened
		<i>Rattus rattus</i>	Roof rat	Less Common
	Muridae	<i>Tatera indica</i>	Indian gerbil	Less Common
		<i>Mus musculus</i>	House mouse	Less Common
	Sciuridae	<i>Funambulus pennantii</i>	Five stripe Palm Squirrel	Less Common
Carnivora	Herpestidae	<i>Herpestes javanicus</i>	Small indian mongoose	Less Common
	Felidae	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	Desert Cat	Data deficient
	Canidae	<i>Canis lupus</i>	Domestic dog	Common

Table 5. Status of Reptilian Species observed.

Orders	Families	Scientific Name	Common Name	Status
Squamata	Varanidae	<i>Varanus flavescens</i>	Yellow Monitor	Threatened
		<i>Varanus bengalensis</i>	Bengal Monitor	Threatened
	Colubridae	<i>Spalerosophis diadema</i>	Blotched Diadem Snake	Threatened
		<i>Psammophis leithii</i>	Sindhi ribbon Snake	Threatened
	Viperidae	<i>Echis carinatus</i>	Saw-Scaled viper	Threatened
	Agamidae	<i>Calotes versicolor</i>	Common tree lizard	Data deficient
	Elapidae	<i>Naja naja</i>	Black Cobra	Near threatened
Gekkonidae	<i>Hemidactylus flaviviridis</i>	Yellow belly common House Gecko)	Threatened	

Table 6. Status of amphibian species observed.

Order	Family	Scientific Name	Common Name	Status
Anura	Bufonidae	<i>Bufo melanostictus</i>	Common Asian Toad	Less Common
	Ranidae	<i>Hoplobatrachus tigerinus</i>	Tiger Frog/Bull Frog	Rare
		<i>Limnonectes limnocharis</i>	Indian Cricket Frog	Rare

Table 7. Numbers and Species of Birds observed.

Order	Family	Scientific Name	Common Name	Average no of individuals throughout the year	pi	Ln(pi)	pi*Ln(pi)	-PI*ln(pi)
Ciconiiformes	Ardeidae	<i>Ardeola grayii</i>	Indian Pond Heron	1.66	0.001555327	0.001555	2.41904E-06	-2.41904E-06
Accipitriformes	Accipitridae	<i>Milvus migrans</i>	Black Kite	164.83	0.154436428	0.154436	0.02385061	-0.02385061
		<i>Accipiter badius</i>	Central Asian Shikra	8.75	0.008198257	0.008198	6.72114E-05	-6.72114E-05
		<i>Circaetus gallicus</i>	Short-toed Eagle	9	0.008432493	0.008432	7.11069E-05	-7.11069E-05
Galliformes	Phasianidae	<i>Francolinus francolinus</i>	Black Partridge	4	0.003747775	0.003748	1.40458E-05	-1.40458E-05
		<i>Francolinus pondicerianus</i>	Grey Partridge	6.5	0.006090134	0.00609	3.70897E-05	-3.70897E-05
Charadriiformes	Charadriidae	<i>Vanellus</i>	Red	11.28	0.010568725	0.010569	0.000111698	-

		<i>indicus</i>	Wattled Lapwing					0.000111698
Columbiformes	Columbidae	<i>Columba livia</i>	Blue Rock Pigeon	381.58	0.357518973	0.357519	0.127819816	-0.127819816
		<i>Streptopelia senegalensis</i>	Little Brown or Senegal Dove	10.45	0.009791062	0.009791	9.58649E-05	-9.58649E-05
Psittaciformes	Psittacidae	<i>Psittacula krameri</i>	Rose ringed Parakeet	5	1072.3	1072.3	1149827.29	-1149827.29
Cuculiformes	Cuculidae	<i>Eudynamis scolopacea</i>	Indian Koel	17.58	0.01647147	0.016471	0.000271309	-0.000271309
		<i>Taccocua leschenaultia</i>	Western Sirkeer Cuckoo	20.66	0.019357257	0.019357	0.000374703	-0.000374703
		<i>Centropus sinensis</i>	Common Crow-Pheasant or Coucal	1.5	0.001405416	0.001405	1.97519E-06	-1.97519E-06
Coraciiformes	Alcedinidae	<i>Halcyon smyrensis</i>	White breasted Kingfisher	4	0.003747775	0.003748	1.40458E-05	-1.40458E-05
	Meropidae	<i>Merops orientalis</i>	Sind Small Green Bee-eater	23	0.021549705	0.02155	0.00046439	-0.00046439
Passeriformes	Alaudidae	<i>Ammomanes deserti</i>	Desert Lark	8.6	0.008057716	0.008058	6.49268E-05	-6.49268E-05
		<i>Galerida cristata</i>	Crested Lark	12	0.011243324	0.011243	0.000126412	-0.000126412
	Hirundinidae	<i>Hirundo daurica</i>	Redrumped Swallow	1	0.000936944	0.000937	8.77863E-07	-8.77863E-07
	Laniidae	<i>Lanius isabellinus</i>	Rufous-tailed or Isabelline Shrike	10.2	0.009556826	0.009557	9.13329E-05	-9.13329E-05
		<i>Lanius vittatus</i>	Baybacked Shrike	10	0.009369437	0.009369	8.77863E-05	-8.77863E-05
	Dicruridae	<i>Dicrurus adsimilis</i>	Black Drongo	1.875	0.001756769	0.001757	3.08624E-06	-3.08624E-06
	Sturnidae	<i>Acridotheres ginginianus</i>	Bank Myna	63.5	0.059495924	0.059496	0.003539765	-0.003539765
		<i>Acridotheres tristis</i>	Indian Myna	22.28	0.020875105	0.020875	0.00043577	-0.00043577
	Corvidae	<i>Corvus splendens</i>	Sind House Crow	105.58	0.098922515	0.098923	0.009785664	-0.009785664
Pyconotidae	<i>Pycnonotus leucogenys</i>	White-cheeked	6.5	0.006090134	0.00609	3.70897E-05	-3.70897E-05	

			Bulbul					
		<i>Pycnonotus cafer</i>	Red-vented Bulbul	8.75	0.008198257	0.008198	6.72114E-05	-6.72114E-05
	Timaliidae	<i>Turdoides caudatus</i>	Common Babbler	15	0.014054155	0.014054	0.000197519	-0.000197519
		<i>Turdoides striatus</i>	Sind Jungle Babbler	8.6	0.008057716	0.008058	6.49268E-05	-6.49268E-05
	Sylviidae	<i>Sylvia curruca</i>	Lesser White throat	8.66	0.008113932	0.008114	6.58359E-05	-6.58359E-05
		<i>Phylloscopus collybita</i>	Common Chiffchaff	6.5	0.006090134	0.00609	3.70897E-05	-3.70897E-05
	Turdidae	<i>Saxicola caprata</i>	Pied Bush Chat	27.8	0.026047035	0.026047	0.000678448	-0.000678448
		<i>Saxicoloides fulicata</i>	Indian Robin	11.125	0.010423499	0.010423	0.000108649	-0.000108649
	Motacillidae	<i>Motacilla alba</i>	White or Pied Wagtail	4	0.003747775	0.003748	1.40458E-05	-1.40458E-05
	Nectariniidae	<i>Nectarinia asiatica</i>	Purple Sunbird	1	0.000936944	0.000937	8.77863E-07	-8.77863E-07
	Passeridae	<i>Passer domesticus</i>	House Sparrow	35.54	0.033298979	0.033299	0.001108822	-0.001108822
		<i>Passer pyrrhonotus</i>	Sind Jungle Sparrow	28	0.026234423	0.026234	0.000688245	-0.000688245
	Ploceidae	<i>Ploceus manyar</i>	Streaked Weaver Bird	1	0.000936944	0.000937	8.77863E-07	-8.77863E-07
			total	1067.3	1073.295315	1073.295	1149827.46	-1149827.5

Figure 1. Graphical representation of average no of individual throughout the year.

Discussion

According to field survey from January 2024 to December 2024, the numbers of birds, mammals, reptiles and amphibians were varied across the Karachi East. In general, along the urban and peri-urban areas of the district, the biodiversity is low. Peripheral areas showed highest biodiversity, as these areas held most complex vegetation with trees, shrubs, tall grasses and herbs. There is a serious decline in biodiversity had been observed during the present study mainly due to social disturbance and the results indicate that human activities are rapidly changing the ecology of the area that could affect the composition and distribution of the biodiversity in the Karachi East. Serious threats to the fauna in the study area was found to be habitat destruction and alteration, anthropogenic activities (directly or indirectly) badly effects on them and result in loss of biodiversity in the area. There was no greater biodiversity of mammals in the district and only 10 species of mammals were recoded.

Recommendations

- Action may be taken to control pollution in the Karachi east as it is one of the main habitats for biodiversity in Karachi.
- Public awareness may be created through the material about wildlife and environmental protection and for the conservation and sustainable utilization of the natural resources

and formulation of species recovery plan for threatened species of the area.

- Master plans may be built up to make expansion of campus in a premeditated manner to avoid severe damage to wildlife and its habitats.
- It has been observed that periurban areas supported more biodiversity as compared to urban areas and the areas with more vegetation covers, had more richness of species while species richness is declined where there was less vegetation therefore it has been recommended that green spaces should be designed for both social and for conservation purpose because the structural diversification of trees within green spaces, a significant aspect, in supporting increased level of species abundance of avianfauna.
- Plans should be made for proper disposal of garbage in the campus and dumping of waste materials in open areas should be strictly banned.
- In addition water pots should be placed for thirsty birds. The water pots can also be placed at regular intervals along roadsides beneath the trees so that they can be filled when the trees are watered.

Before present study, no scientific data has been reported about the population and status of mammalian, reptilian and amphibian fauna of Karachi East Hopefully, this study will serve as a baseline for further research and future management plan.

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